

USAGE OF THE EMERGENCY TERMS (LEXIS) IN THE CONTEXT (IN THE DIFFERENT TEXTS)

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Annotation: A key component of emergency management is the specific terms used in its communication process, although official sources focus on emergency warnings, communication in emergency management is a two-way process and always requires oversight by traditional agencies. This article also examines the terms and language units used in emergencies to describe people involved in disasters and whether terms can be found in other emergency and non-emergency contexts.

Key words: *Emergency term, context, disaster victim, disaster survivor, Emergency management personnel, society communication, member of the community, resident, client, beneficiary and service user.*

INTRODUCTION

Members of society now prefer to communicate using many different databases, especially when people try to explain and express interest in different disasters happening on earth, whereas emergencies have become a context that attracts everyone. . And grassroots people are recognized as important players who can provide context and multiple ways of communicating around disasters. This process is reflected in the National Disaster Response Strategy: Disaster Response in Context calls for a shift in communication focus from top-down messages to engaging individuals and communities at the grassroots level so that they understand disaster risks and take ownership of managing those risks. (National

Strategy for Disaster Resilience 2011)¹

In recent years, leaders of response-oriented organizations have acknowledged that emergency communication has become more important than response activities.

While attention to words and language and their potential for action has not been extensively studied in the field of emergency management, it has been in other fields such as civil rights, criminology, and gender studies. Language use has been shown to influence behavior and actions across time.²

Methodology

As part of a 2013 Fulbright Fellowship, former US Department of Homeland Security Deputy Assistant Secretary Bob Jensen made a series of presentations to emergency managers in Australia and shared his experience of various disasters in partnership with the Federal. United States Emergency Management Agency (FEMA). On several occasions, he said, "Once we [FEMA] stopped calling people 'victims,' it changed the way we worked with them." Jensen's thinking showed that significant changes in attitudes and behavior could be achieved through changes in language.³

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² Alter A 2013, The Power of Names. The New Yorker.

³ <https://knowledge.aidr.org.au/resources/ajem-oct-2015-the-words-we-use-and-the-stories-we-tell-the-impacts-language-has-on-the-actions-and-perceptions-of-emergency-managers/>

showed that significant changes in attitudes and behavior could be achieved through changes in language.

To explore this, a questionnaire was developed to investigate how the language used to describe the different players in an emergency situation shapes the behavior of emergency managers. In this questionnaire, the most frequently used terms and their meanings are established: victim, survivor, emergency management personnel.

At this point, it should be noted that although this survey was conducted in America, applying it to society, these were the most commonly used sentences among the people when talking about situations in the verbal emergency. At this point, it should be said that the Uzbek people like to approach various events with different theories, especially the people who like to react to a disaster and discuss it with others. From this point of view, we organized an oral questionnaire similar to this questionnaire. It turned out that the above 3 terms are often used by community residents and members of society.

Data collection

These three names or labels are commonly used in emergency management policies, activities, manuals, and training. A paper-based survey (completed anonymously) was distributed to attendees at the 2014 Emergency Media and Public Relations (EMPA) conferences in Auckland and Canberra⁴. Attendees at these conferences were invited to complete a survey, a total of 49 were collected in Auckland, and a week later, attendees at the Canberra EMPA conference completed 69 surveys⁵. EMPA conference attendees represent emergency

⁴ <https://knowledge.aidr.org.au/resources/ajem-oct-2015-the-words-we-use-and-the-stories-we-tell-the-impacts-language-has-on-the-actions-and-perceptions-of-emergency-managers/>

⁵ Kaniasty K., Norris F. The experience of disaster: individuals and communities sharing trauma. In: Gist R., Lubin B., editors. Response to Disaster: Psychosocial, Ecological, and Community Approaches. Taylor & Francis; Washington, DC: 1999. pp. 25–61.

management agencies, the military, government, non-governmental organizations, research institutions, media and private sector organizations. Conference participants were interested in communications and emergency management, were generally highly educated, and represented a balanced gender mix.

This activity is not intended to generate quantitative data or perform statistical analysis. Rather, it was a quick test to see if engagement activity and any patterns emerged. It was also a resource for participants to actively express their attitudes and expectations when certain words were used. The feedback from the participants provided interesting insight into some of the attitudes that are prevalent in the emergency management sector.

Analysis

Although the words "victim" and "survivor" are not widely discussed in the context of emergency management, they are often discussed in the inter-community context, where they are discussed in relation to international development, conflict and violence. . This empirical examination of two terms helps to explain the story and character surrounding them as terms that have become part of everyday language. These two terms, which appear in different contexts among the community, are widely discussed (Table 1).

VICTIM	SURVIVOR
The word ‘victim’ is a derivative of the Latin word <i>victima</i> , meaning sacrificial animal. The oldest record of using the word to refer to a human occurred during the Renaissance period in reference to Jesus Christ. Following this, the term began to be used more colloquially to	The term ‘survivor’ is used in many different contexts. A rise in the term ‘survivor’ was seen in the 1960s and 1970s and was used by groups of people who had previously been portrayed

refer to those suffering innocently from bad luck or other people's criminal behaviours⁶. The origins of some of the traits that are given to victims today—blameless, passive and needy—can be linked to this time. Many modern European, Asian and Arabic languages have more formally adopted 'victim' to refer to someone who has had a crime or offence perpetrated against them. While originally used in criminology as a neutral term to refer to a person who has suffered an act of crime, the word 'victim' has become increasingly loaded⁷. Sexual violence activists often reject the term because of its implied passivity and weakness⁸ and aid agencies that portray end-users as 'victims' can be criticised for being paternalistic and inflammatory in their portrayal of helplessness in order to increase donations. The deliberate 'victimisation' of aid recipients for gain is sometimes cynically referred to as 'poverty porn'⁹.

as weak or helpless. These included those who had survived the Holocaust, sexual assault, rape and incest, and people affected by health conditions such as cancer. In the same era the word was used increasingly in psychotherapy, where the ultimate aim of a therapist was to assist 'victims' to become 'survivors'. The term 'survivor' has been cast as an opposing identity to that of the victim. While both characters may have undergone something painful or traumatic that was outside of their control, the victim is seen to be immobilised and defeated by the experience, while the survivor rises above the adversity they face¹⁰.

⁶ Mileti D.S., Sorensen J.H. Oak Ridge National Lab.; TN (USA): 1990. Communication of Emergency Public Warnings: A Social Science Perspective and State-Of-The-Art Assessment (No. ORNL-6609)

⁷ McLeer A 1998, Saving the victim: Recuperating the language of the victim and reassessing global feminism. *Hypatia*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 41–55.

⁸ Leisenring A 2006, Confronting 'Victim' Discourses: The Identity Work of Battered Women. *Symbolic Interaction*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 307–330.

⁹ Cameron J & Haanstra A 2008, Development Made Sexy: How it happened and what it means. *Third World Quarterly*, vol 29, no. 8, pp. 1475–1489.

Table 1. Commentary on the terms survivor and victim

Although other terms are many and widely used in disaster management, victim and survivor are the two most commonly interpreted terms. Other titles include 'member of the community', 'resident', 'client', 'beneficiary' and 'service user'. Each of these terms presents its own challenges (for example, they may not represent people who are affected by a natural disaster but do not live in a geographic area; people outside the agency responsible for that geographic area are almost always However, in many contexts such as business, land ownership, communication, television, information, technology, these terms are also widely used.

Result

During this study, respondents were asked to list five words or phrases that describe disaster victims, disaster survivors, and emergency management personnel. They were then given a list of 38 words and sentences; some describe properties or essences, while others describe actions. They were asked to identify which words and sentences were associated with their perceptions of disaster victims, disaster survivors, and emergency management personnel (Table 1).

Although the responses given by the participants were predictable, given the general responsibility focus in emergency management policy, the emerging trends were quite interesting.

Disaster victim	Disaster survivor	Emergency management personnel
Afraid	Lucky	Action oriented
Damaged	Resilient	Capable
Upset	Resourceful	Informed

¹⁰ Orgad S 2009, The survivor in contemporary culture and public discourse: A genealogy. The Communication Review, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 132–161.

Weak	Strong	Practical
Worried	Traumatized	Resourceful

Table 1: Features most frequently used when participants were asked to select words and sentences from a list to describe emergency roles.

Discussion

There are key trends that warrant further investigation; was how differently emergency management personnel viewed themselves and their colleagues in relation to victims and survivors. The results of this exercise show that the perception of emergency managers is that there is still a perception that emergency management personnel have superior knowledge, attitudes and skills compared to the rest of society. Key documents such as the National Disaster Resilience Strategy emphasize that building community resilience in emergency management requires increasing community and citizen-generated engagement rather than relying on top-down formal responses. Without ignoring the painstaking experience of many professionals in this field, it teaches others in society to feel responsible for the skills and knowledge they can bring to these situations.

A further trend that emerged from the responses shows a stark difference in the perception of 'victim' compared to 'survivor'. Participants consistently viewed victims as weaker, less knowledgeable, less fortunate, less educated, and less educated than survivors. A simplistic analysis suggests that participants viewed survivors through a “strengths-based” lens and victims through a “deficit” lens. Optimistically, this suggests that by deliberately changing language, improving education for emergency managers, and strengthening team collaboration, profound changes can be made with very small actions.

Conclusion

The trends emerging from this simple activity suggest that emergency management planners, practitioners, and communicators can learn from other

fields, such as public health and community development, where language has been deliberately altered. From a public perspective, it shows a simplistic approach to some of the terms used in emergency situations, which implies the need to build public knowledge and attitudes and think differently about emergency situations. It should be said here that the terms used in emergency situations are also widely used in other fields, and looking at concepts from the perspective of society shows that they are sometimes narrow, not depending on different worldviews and fields.

If the emergency management sector is committed to sharing responsibility for fostering truly resilient communities, a cultural shift in how community members are perceived by the sector will first require creating the right perspective on events. . Sector leaders and communicators can use different terms as peers with team members. Deliberately changing the language we use is fine, but the key to making these changes a reality is being able to use the terms correctly in different contexts.

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